

Concepts of language and culture

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Abstract. The article considers the main theories and concepts of co-study of language and culture that appeared in English pedagogy in the late 20th - early 20th centuries. It is stated that socio-cultural, economic factors, and political events contributed to the fact that a foreign language has become a real means of communication, a factor in understanding and bringing people of different cultures closer together, their interaction, a source of information about the world, a way of self-development, and expansion of professional knowledge. Interest in the communicative and cultural components of the discipline "Foreign Language" entailed a change in the goal-value attitudes, content, methods, i.e. the entire structure of the organization of the educational process, contributed to a significant change in approaches to its teaching, namely, mandatory study in the context of culture.

Key words: foreign language; culture; language education; dialogue of cultures; sociocultural approach; intercultural communication; multicultural education; foreign language education.

Introduction

At the end of the 20th - beginning of the 21st century, a foreign language became a real means of communication, a factor in understanding and bringing people of different cultures closer together, their interaction, a source of information about the world, a way of self-development, and improvement of professional knowledge. The expansion of intercultural contacts and, as a consequence, the rapprochement of cultures acutely raises the question of the productivity of intercultural interaction.

The rapidly changing conditions of international partnership have entailed the need to solve many complex issues, so the problem of intercultural communication, the quality of which determines the paths of human development, becomes an important object of research in the humanities. In accordance with this, special attention is paid to increasing the effectiveness of studying foreign languages, and, consequently, the role and place of the academic discipline "Foreign Language" are increasing, which through the study of the language and culture of the country not only forms linguistic and cultural knowledge, but also provides experience in socio-cultural and intercultural communication.

A characteristic feature of language education is the orientation towards the intercultural aspect of language acquisition, which prompted teachers and methodologists to rethink the existing traditional approaches to its study, as well as to develop more productive ways of mastering another culture. At this period, the emergence and substantiation of new theories and concepts of studying a foreign language from the standpoint of culture are observed in domestic pedagogy, which found its expression in the transformation and modernization of the theoretical foundations of teaching a foreign language.

Methodology

The basis for the development of new theories and concepts was the principle of dialogue of cultures, which was revealed by M.M. Bakhtin, V.S. Bibler, S.Yu. Kurganov and other scientists. In the works of scientists, the emphasis is placed on the fact that any training should be built as a

dialogue of various historically existing logics, cultures, ways of understanding (ancient, medieval, modern, contemporary). M.M. Bakhtin wrote that “only in communication, in the interaction of man with man, the man in man is revealed both for others and for himself... The personality is alive only in its address to others, which means that the personality exists where there is dialogue” [1. P. 40]. During the dialogue, a special communication between people arises, in which the participants not only “show certain “the boundaries of ancient, medieval and other thinking, but, above all, they ‘feel’ their own view of the world”.

This idea is very important, since ignorance of the culture of another people, its mentality leads to interethnic misunderstandings and confrontation. As D.S. Likhachev noted, each of the cultures of the past or another country becomes "their own culture" for an intelligent person, since knowledge of one's own is associated with knowledge of someone else's. It was this understanding of the open and tolerant process of cultural communication that allowed D.S. Likhachev to assert that culture is the universal foundation of human existence, the main source of humanization of human history.

Teachers develop the basic provisions of the cultural approach to teaching the humanities, new approaches to the content of education, including language, and study the mechanisms of cultural acquisition. Thus, the concept of E.V. Bondarevskaya substantiates the position on the expediency of education in the context of culture. N.E. Shchurkova considers the organization of education as a factor in the entry of english society into world culture. Research by a group of psychologists headed by I.A. Zimnyaya is based on the understanding of education as a process of forming a person's attitude to the world.

Consequently, the task of education, as well as upbringing in general, is the formation of personality by transmitting accumulated culture. The assimilation of culture presupposes the transformation in the consciousness of the personality of the products of social spiritual activity or social experience, thanks to which the formation of the culture of the personality occurs.

Study

The specificity of a foreign language as an academic subject is that its teaching involves mastering not only the foreign language itself, but also familiarization with the literature, history and, in general, the culture of the language being studied. According to S.G. Ter-Minasova, the change in the essential approach "required an immediate and fundamental revision of both the general methodology and specific methods and techniques of teaching foreign languages". In this regard, academic teachers, methodologists, and specialists in the field of studying foreign languages began to develop productive options for studying a foreign language in the context of culture. Their modeling was based on a didactically oriented sociological analysis of the language learning environment, the socio-cultural context of studying a foreign language, and special attention was paid to the socio-cultural features of languages and cultures.

Among the studies, first of all, I would like to highlight the works of V.V. Safonova “Sociocultural approach to teaching a foreign language as a specialty” (1992), V.P. Furmanova “Intercultural communicative competence and cultural-linguistic pragmatics in the theory and practice of teaching foreign languages” (1994), E.I. Passov “The concept of communicative foreign language education” (2000) and P.V. Sysoev “The concept of linguistic multicultural education” (2003).

The unifying principle of these works is that they focus on the need to study language and culture together. Despite some differences in scientific concepts, the conclusion about the need and importance of teaching a language, and in particular a foreign language, as a component of culture is generally recognized.

Thus, V. V. Safonova sees the significance of the sociocultural approach in the fact that it captures the understanding of culture as a broad complex of social phenomena that represent the results and means of social functioning and development.

It is entirely possible to agree with the scientists, whose identical ideas are separated by a huge period of time, that the wording "teaching a foreign language" does not correspond to the content, the completeness of the process, since the emphasis is on "teaching a language", while in the process of learning a foreign language itself there is a huge educational potential, because not only the language is studied, but also the culture of another people. It is this important substantive component that is not objectified in the title.

E. I. Passov points out that the purpose of teaching a foreign language is not only purely academic (communication skills, mastery of communicative competence), but also educational (education of a spiritual person). In this context, he suggests using the term "foreign language education" rather than the term "foreign language teaching". He views a foreign language (due to its unique educational opportunities) not as an "academic subject", but as an "educational discipline" with enormous potential, capable of making a significant contribution to the development of a person as an individual.

Defining the main goal of foreign language education as the formation of a spiritual person, E.I. Passov believes that a spiritual person is not someone who knows and can do something, but someone who has stable guidelines that govern his activities in any area: a culture of constructive creative work, a culture of reasonable consumption, a culture of humanistic communication, a culture of knowledge, a culture worldview, the culture of aesthetic assimilation of reality. He points out that in this case individuality is distinguished by the ability to create and enrich culture, it integrates freedom of creativity and responsibility. Therefore, he views the education system as a social institution for the development of individuality as a subject of culture.

Currently, one of the problems in the field of teaching foreign languages, the need for a solution to which is indicated by V.V. Safonova, is a more intensive development of such a field of scientific knowledge as language pedagogy, revealing the essence and patterns of bilingual, as well as multilingual multicultural education. Language pedagogy, in her opinion, determines "the range of variability of paths, principles, strategies and methods of co-study of languages and cultures depending on socio-cultural factors that significantly affect the effectiveness of intercultural interaction of people in the multilingual, multicultural world of the 21st century, which is quite contradictory, burdened by political, economic and cultural conflicts and global interdependence". That is why, according to V.V. Safonova, the dialogue of cultures and civilizations should become a fundamental methodological principle in modern language pedagogy.

Conclusions

Thus, at the end of the 20th - beginning of the 21st century, there was an essential change in the goal-value bases of teaching the subject "Foreign Language". The cultural paradigm of education has outlined a strategic task for it - mandatory study of language in the context of culture. Familiarization with the culture of the country of the studied language influences the development of the personality of students on the basis of the new culture in its dialogue with the native one. The concepts presented in the article have become innovative, united by a common cultural idea - the idea of co-studying language and culture, which has had a significant impact both on the substantive component of the subject "Foreign Language" and on the methodology of its teaching.

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